

Original Research Report

Perceived Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education on the Management of the Hospitality Industry in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The paper investigated the impact of entrepreneurship education on hospitality industry management in Benue State, Nigeria. To cicerone, the research, three study purposes, and three research questions were developed. The study's population consists of all 2000 registered restaurants and bars in Makurdi. The random sampling technique was used, and the sample size was 200 panelists plus restaurant and bar owners. The mean rating of respondents was calculated using a five-point Likert scale. Three experts logically validated the survey, yielding a reliability index of.871. The study yielded the following results: respondents believed that entrepreneurship education would increase creativity, competition, brainstorming, and innovation in hospitality management. Three recommendations were made, including teaching entrepreneurship education as a course in a tertiary institution and teaching entrepreneurship education to hospitality industry professionals.

Keywords: Brainstorming, Creativity, Entrepreneurship Education, Hospitality, Innovation

1. Introduction

Education has long been touted as one of the most visible ways out of poverty, but with an increasing number of unemployed university graduates, this claim is no longer valid. It is now clear that unless citizens are exposed to the proper education, unemployment will continue unabated. Incorporating entrepreneurship education into the curriculum is one way to ensure that education helps to address national and global unemployment. Entrepreneurship education has the potential to be viewed as a driver of economic development and job creation in any society. It also entails rebranding the educational culture to ensure a successful outcome. (Lee et al., 2006).

This implies that entrepreneurship education plays an important role in human empowerment and job creation because entrepreneurs employ more people through their businesses, thereby

boosting economic development.

The primary goal of entrepreneurship education is to provide students with the necessary skills and capacities for the workplace. Evans-Obinna (2016) defined entrepreneurship education as the process by which individuals acquire a broad set of competencies that can result in greater social and economic benefits to the individuals. Entrepreneurship education, according to Enu (2012), is a type of education that seeks to provide students with knowledge, skills, attitudes, and motivation for entrepreneurial success in any aspect of human endeavors. Enu (2012) goes on to say that entrepreneurship education prepares people to seek out investment opportunities and maximize the returns on those investments.

The hospitality industry of Benue state has become a topic of discourse as there appears to be no local government area that is not affected by the stagnation of the hospitality industry in the state. The state is ranked below the likes of Lagos, Rivers, Cross River, and Imo states in the hospitality industry whereas the state is the food basket of the country and home to several tourist attraction sites (Enu, 2012). Education has always been portrayed as one of the most visible ways out of poverty, as well as one of the most effective ways to boost creativity and innovation among undergraduates and graduates in the hospitality industry. Except for hospitality professionals who are exposed to the proper form of education, Benue State's hospitality industry will continue to play second fiddle to states such as Rivers and Lagos. One way to ensure that entrepreneurship education helps to address the backlogs in the Benue State hospitality industry is to incorporate a type of entrepreneurship education known as "Entrepretality" into the curriculum of university students studying hospitality and among hospitality professionals (Evans-Obinna, 2016).

According to Li (2009), the term "Entrepretality" was coined from the term "Entrepreneurship and Hospitality" Arogundade (2011) in her published article, asserted Entrepreneurship education: is An imperative for sustainable development in Nigeria. Entrepretality is the process of using available resources to create value by improving the service-value proposition to a customer, client, or other beings, which in turn boosts creativity and innovation in the hospitality industry (Matlay, 2005). Although the definition of entrepreneurship in hospitality is limiting because it solely focuses on starting a new venture creation and neglects to look at the foundation of hospitality education, creating a service-value proposition to a customer, entrepreneurship in hospitality in academia will enhance service value in the hospitality industry in Benue state, Nigeria. Entrepreneurship education can be incorporated into hospitality by including it in the hospitality department's curriculum and naming it Entrepretality, as well as creating a separate study for Entrepretality so that already existing professionals can acquire new skills in Entrepretality and stay current with innovative and creative ideas in the hospitality industry while mastering the managerial attributes of the hospitality industry. Entrepretality can be taught in our tertiary institutions or at the professional level through a meal design course/module, entertainment course, or bartending course. If this module is stressed and properly taught, it will not only improve the type of delicacies but also the standard of hospitality ranking in Benue state, Nigeria.

Developed countries such as the United States, England, and Canada are currently running hospitality entrepreneurship programs in tertiary institutions to improve students' concentration, practical experience, management, creativity, and innovation in the hospitality industry. That is why, in most developed countries, receptionists, bartenders, and service personnel are courteous and always ready to create a new menu from scratch using the country's already-established food items (Tope, 2014). Benue state's hospitality industry has been bedridden for years, with the state ranking

at zero or low in the hospitality industry. Hospitality is concerned with how we treat our customers, how excellent our services are, and how elegant and spiced up our services are. Benue is Nigeria's food basket, but it has failed to live up to expectations over the years. Benue state is known for having fertile land that produces various varieties of food, but how to use such a great asset of produce varieties to her advantage has been a measure problem, the lack of 5-star hospitality destination spot and etiquette gave birth to this study perceived effectiveness of entrepreneurship education on the management of the hospitality industry in Benue State.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The hospitality industry is almost dead in Benue state as there has been a constant repetition of meals and drinks all over bars and hotels in the state, and there are no new menus or a new mixture of drinks across the state. Restaurants, bars, and hotels are not known for having any insignia or any delicacies of drinks or anything for which they are known. This repetitive way of hospitality has not only affected the state but the country at large. Nevertheless, some states within the country have managed to surpass this derogatory form of hospitality. The lack of entrepreneurship education on the management of the hospitality industry (Entrepreneurship) in Benue State inspired this study, which sought to determine the perceived effect of entrepreneurship education on the management of the hospitality industry in Benue State, Nigeria.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The study's main goal was to determine the perceived effect of entrepreneurship education on hospitality industry management in Benue State, Nigeria. Other specific goals include:

- (a) Examine the effect of entrepreneurship education on the management of the Hospitality industry in Benue State.
- (b) Analyze the effect of entrepreneurship education on Creativity within the hospitality industry in Benue State.
- (c) Analyze the effect of entrepreneurship education on innovation within the hospitality industry in Benue State.

1.3. Research Questions

- (a) How does entrepreneurship education affect the management of the Hospitality industry in Benue State?
- (b) How effective is Entrepreneurship education on creativity in the hospitality industry of Benue State?
- (c) How effective is Entrepreneurship education on Innovation in the hospitality industry of Benue State?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study was conducted using a survey design, which is a type of research design in which the primary method of data collection is by research survey. A survey is used as a tool by researchers to gather information for a better understanding of individuals' or groups' perspectives on a specific concept or topic (Mills, 2021).

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The researchers got approval from Restaurant and Bar Owners Association in Benue state to effectively survey her members. The approval was granted after the union understood the essence of the study was for research purposes only. Informed consent was obtained verbally from respondents.

2.2. Area of the Study

The research was conducted in Makurdi, Benue State. The state capital was established in the early 1920s and rose to prominence when it became the headquarters of the then-Benue Province in 1927. Because it is a river port, companies such as United Africa Company of Nigeria and John Holt Plc have established trading depots there. When the Railway Bridge was completed and opened in 1932, it further enhanced its commercial status. The town became the capital of Benue State in 1976 and now serves as the headquarters of the Makurdi Local Government Area. The study was conducted in Makurdi because it is Nigeria's food capital and should be the best-ranked city in terms of hospitality.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population consisted of all 2000 registered restaurants and bars in Makurdi, Nigeria's capital. The study's sample size was 100 restaurant and bar owners and 100 bar owners in Makurdi. The sample consisted of 150 females and 50 males, with an average age of 35 years. The random sampling technique was used for the study's sampling. This method was used to select 200 panelists from Makurdi's restaurant and bar owners.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

The researcher created a five-point Likert Scale questionnaire to collect data. The questionnaire was used to collect data on the "Perceived Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education on Hospitality Industry Management Questionnaire." The questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B; Section A is about the respondents' socioeconomic characteristics, such as gender and occupation. Section B included items used to assess the impact of the variables on hospitality.

Five-point Likert score

- 5 - Extremely Effective (EE)
- 4 - Highly Effective (HE)
- 3 - Very Effective (VE)
- 2 - Slightly Effective (SE)
- 1 - Not Effective (NE)

Three experts in family and human development from Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike and two lecturers from the Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku face validated the instrument. The instrument had an alpha reliability coefficient of 0.871.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The questionnaire was distributed to respondents by the researchers with the assistance of two research assistants, and the distributed samples were retrieved after two weeks by the research assistants, who were properly trained on how to interact with and guide respondents on how to fill out the survey.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The descriptive statistics method was used to analyze data collected from respondents via research assistants because it displays the mean, median, mode, and standard deviation of the variables. SPSS 28 was used as the software. The research question was analyzed using a mean rating. In calculating the effectiveness of the variables in the hospitality industry management, any

mean rating greater than or equal to 2.5 was accepted, whereas any mean rating less than 2.5 was rejected.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* How does entrepreneurship education affect the management of the Hospitality industry in Benue State?

Table 1: How entrepreneurship education affects the management of the Hospitality industry in Benue State.

Items	$\bar{X}_1$	$\bar{X}_2$	$\bar{X}_3$	$\bar{X}_G$	SD	Remark
Competition	2	1	4	2.33	1.52	Slightly Effective
Creativity	3	3	5	3.66	1.15	Very Effective
Brain Storming	4	3	3	3.33	0.5	Very Effective
Innovation	2	2	4	2.66	1.15	Slightly Effective
Pooled Mean	2.75	2.25	4	3	0.90	Very Effective

Keys: $\bar{X}_1$ =Mean Response of restaurant owners, $\bar{X}_2$ = Mean Response of bar owners, $\bar{X}_3$ = Mean Response of customers, $\bar{X}_G$ = Average Mean rating of all Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 1 showed the pooled mean of respondents: restaurant owners =2.75, bar owners = 2.25, and customers = 4. This implies that restaurant owners and customers agreed that entrepreneurship education has a positive effect on the management of the hospitality industry in Benue State. The above assertion is in contrast to bar owners whose mean rating was 2.25 and below the decision on the rule of 2.5. Despite bar owners contrasting views on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education on the management of the hospitality industry, the average mean rating of 3 is above the cut-off mark of 2.5 which implies that a large percentage of the respondents agrees that entrepreneurship education has a positive impact on creativity, innovation, brainstorming, competition and management of the hospitality industry.

3.2. *Research question two:* How effective is entrepreneurship education on creativity in the hospitality industry of Benue State?

Table 2: Mean rating on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education on creativity in the hospitality industry of Benue State.

Items	$\bar{X}_1$	$\bar{X}_2$	$\bar{X}_3$	$\bar{X}_G$	SD	Remark
Competition	3	2	4	3.00	1.00	Very Effective
Creativity	2	3	2	2.33	0.55	Slightly Effective
Brain Storming	3	2	3	2.66	0.55	Slightly Effective
Innovation	3	3	4	3.00	1.00	Very Effective
Pooled Mean	2.5	2.5	3.25	2.75	0.43	Slightly Effective

Keys: $\bar{X}_1$ =Mean Response of restaurant owners, $\bar{X}_2$ = Mean Response of bar owners, $\bar{X}_3$ = Mean Response of customers, $\bar{X}_G$ = Average Mean rating of all Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 2 showed the mean of restaurant owners = 2.5, bar owners = 2.5, and customers = 3.25 which depicts that restaurant owners, bar owners, and customers agree that Entrepreneurship education has a positive effect on the creativity of barmen, servicemen, bar and restaurant owners in the hospitality industry. The average of mean rating of 2.75 depicts that respondents believe that entrepreneurship education can be very effective in the creative aspect of the hospitality industry.

3.3. Research question three: How effective is entrepreneurship education on Innovation in the hospitality industry of Benue State

Table 3: Mean rating on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education on creativity in the hospitality industry of Benue State.

Items	$\bar{X}_1$	$\bar{X}_2$	$\bar{X}_3$	$\bar{X}_G$	SD	Remark
Competition	2	3	1	2.00	1.00	Slightly Effective
Creativity	3	3	2	2.66	0.57	Slightly Effective
Brain Storming	4	3	3	3.33	0.57	Very Effective
Innovation	2	2	4	2.66	1.15	Slightly Effective
Pooled Mean	2.75	2.75	2.5	2.66	0.14	Slightly Effective

Keys: $\bar{X}_1$ =Mean Response of restaurant owners, $\bar{X}_2$ = Mean Response of bar owners, $\bar{X}_3$ = Mean Response of customers, $\bar{X}_G$ = Average Mean rating of all Respondents, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 3 showed the mean rating of restaurant owners =2.75, bar owners = 2.75, and customers = 2.5 which depicts that restaurant owners, bar owners, and customers agreed that Entrepreneurship education has a positive effect on barmen, servicemen, bar and restaurant owners in the hospitality industry coming up with new innovative ideas. The average of mean rating of 2.66 depicts that respondents agree that entrepreneurship education can be very effective in the innovation aspect of the hospitality industry.

In summary, respondents believed that entrepreneurship education would increase creativity, competition, brainstorming, and innovation in hospitality management. The study's findings are consistent with those of Li (2009), who stated in his published journal an empirical study of corporate entrepreneurship in hospitality companies that entrepreneurship plays a significant role in the hospitality industry by stimulating creativity and innovation. This is also consistent with the findings of Evans-Obinna (2016), who stated in his published journal Entrepreneurship education for self-reliance for economic development in Nigeria that entrepreneurship education increases the chances of the hospitality industry being self-sufficient in terms of skills, servicemen, and personnel. Nonetheless, the findings contrast with those of Arogundade (2011) who stated in her published journal that entrepreneurship education is best used as a form of vocational education and may not fit in perfectly well in the hospitality industry because she believes the hospitality industry alone does not stand as a perfect avenue for entrepreneurship education; she also stated that this type of education will fit mostly into tourism rather than the hospitality industry. The study was constrained by the length of the research as well as the availability and corporations of respondents.

Fund was a major challenge as commuting from my base in Abuja to Makurdi to gather this information was expensive, notwithstanding the financial aggrandizement attached to the data used for the study. Getting access to research material and data related to both the hospitalism and entrepreneurship industry of Benue state Nigeria was not easy, as we hit a brick wall on several occasions to get experts' opinions and data for this research work.

The effectiveness of the Hospitality industry in Benue state Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. Before this study, most barmen, service men, caterers, and restaurant owners do not know that they can incorporate an entrepreneurship mentality into their service in order to boost innovation and creativity. The study has enabled the medulla and thinking faculties of the aforementioned to know they can add flair, style, and class to their services through entrepreneurship in order to boost creativity and innovation in the hospitality industry of Benue state, Nigeria.

4. Conclusion

Entrepreneurship education in form of Entrepreneurship has a positive effect on the management of the Hospitality industry and should be taken seriously in order to boost the GDP of the state and Country. The researchers posit that entrepreneurship education will be very effective in the management of the hospitality industry of Benue state as it promotes creativity and innovative idea, increases competition, and brainstorming among restaurant cum bar owners, servicemen, and barmen across Makurdi town, and the state at large. As a result, entrepreneurship education in the form of Entrepreneurship should be taught in all tertiary institutions in the state to raise awareness of entrepreneurship education in Hospitality as a course. Entrepreneurship education should be taught to existing professionals in the Benue State hospitality industry to improve competition, brainstorming, innovation, creativity, and the management of the state's hospitality industry. To reposition the state hospitality industry, restaurant and bar owners should be willing to learn new skills in the hospitality system through entrepreneurship education.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: KMM and UEN.

Sample collection: KMM and UEN

Formal analysis: KMM and UEN

Funding acquisition: KMM and UEN

Investigation: KMM and UEN.

Methodology: KMM and UEN

Data analysis: KMM and UEN

Writing – original draft, review & editing: KMM and UEN

Data Availability Statement

All of the data used in this were obtained from online sources and Ministry of Commerce and Industry in Benue State, Nigeria.

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